

Perceived Sound Quality of Mechanical Keyboard Switch Mechanisms: A Psychoacoustic Evaluation Using Subjective Ratings and the Annoyance Model

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Abstract

Keyboard enthusiasts often modify their keyboards to enhance the acoustic experience. Despite widespread practices, little research has examined the psychoacoustic factors underlying perceived keyboard sound quality. This study investigates the psychoacoustic parameters that contribute to auditory satisfaction in mechanical keyboard switches. Specifically, it addresses the question: When using a mechanical keyboard for productivity tasks, which switch mechanism is perceived as most audibly satisfying, and which psychoacoustic parameters account for this perception?

A listening-based user experience study was conducted with 17 participants, collecting subjective evaluations and objective psychoacoustic measurements. Psychoacoustic metrics were calculated using Zwicker and Fastl's Psychoacoustic Annoyance model. Analysis of Overall Listening Experience ratings revealed that clicky switches received significantly lower ratings while tactile switches received significantly higher ratings. Psychoacoustic sharpness exhibited a weak negative correlation with quality of experience, and clicky switches demonstrated significantly higher sharpness values than tactile and linear switches.

These findings suggest that increased sharpness, derived within the Psychoacoustic Annoyance framework, may be associated with reduced sound quality in productivity contexts. The results provide guidance for mechanical keyboard design, indicating that controlling high-frequency spectral weighting and sharpness-related characteristics of mechanical switches may improve acoustic comfort. However, given the modest correlation strength and conflicting findings in the prior literature, further research is needed to clarify these relationships.

Keywords

Keyboard Switches, Mechanical Keyboards, Psychoacoustics, Quality of Experience (QoE), Annoyance

1. Introduction

A Mechanical Keyboard is a keyboard with mechanical switches underneath each keycap [1]. These devices have been surging in popularity, driven by a growing community of enthusiasts who modify their hardware to optimize acoustic experience [2]. However, “many enthusiasts do not understand what makes their mechanical keyboards satisfying.” [3] Modifications often rely on onomatopoeic descriptors—such as “thocky”, “clacky”, or “clicky”—rather than empirical

acoustic data.

While sound quality is highly correlated with the user experience (UX) of mechanical keyboards [4, p. 227], little research examines the specific psychoacoustic factors underlying these perceptions. By investigating the psychoacoustic parameters that contribute to auditory satisfaction, this research seeks to provide a framework that mechanical keyboard enthusiasts can use for human-centered hardware design.

Figure 1. Parts of a Mechanical Keyboard by Theresa McDonough [5]

The mechanical switch is the physical mechanism underlying each keycap [6] (see Figure 1). It serves as the primary excitation source in a mechanical keyboard, defining the initial auditory transient that is later colored by the case or keycaps [7]. For this reason, the present study investigates the “Source” of the traditional Source-Path-Receiver model.

Mechanical switches are generally categorized into three primary behaviors: linear, tactile, and clicky. Each provides a distinct tactile and auditory profile. **Linear switches** provide a smooth keystroke with no tactile feedback [8]. **Tactile switches** incorporate a “haptic bump” to signal actuation, while **clicky switches** augment this tactile response with a “click” noise [9, 10]. These three categories represent the fundamental mechanisms upon which modern switch variations are engineered; therefore, evaluating these behaviors is essential for understanding the psychoacoustics of a mechanical keyboard.

Listening attitudes toward mechanical keyboards can be categorized into two roles: the **passive listener** and the **operator** [11]. The passive listener perceives the keyboard’s audio output without tactile feedback, often while engaged in a separate task. The operator is in an active listening state, experiencing both the auditory feedback and tactile response of an actuated switch. Given that this study aims to evaluate the user’s experience, the research is contextualized from the operator’s perspective.

Mechanical keyboards are utilized in two distinct contexts: gaming and productivity. In gaming applications, the emphasis is on fast function and tactile feedback to confirm in-game actions. Productivity-focused hardware is designed for sustained use over extended periods, where the

user’s Quality of Experience (QoE) is critical to maintaining focus.

A study of open-plan offices in China demonstrated that “annoying” sound factors—like keyboard typing—decreased the perceived quality of a passive listener’s working environment [12]. While gaming may prioritize transient feedback, productivity models require a higher degree of acoustic comfort to prevent auditory fatigue.

Thus, this research was guided by the question: “When using a mechanical keyboard for *productivity tasks*, which *switch mechanism* is perceived as most audibly satisfying, and which *psychoacoustic parameters* account for this perception?”

2. Related Works

Loudness and Psychoacoustic Annoyance. Loudness strongly influences the overall experience of a mechanical keyboard, particularly as higher sound levels are associated with user annoyance [7]. Psychoacoustic Annoyance (PA) is defined as a combination of hearing sensations that quantitatively describe the feeling of annoyance. According to Zwicker and Fastl’s [13] Psychoacoustic Annoyance model, annoyance is primarily driven by loudness(N), which accounts for a dominant portion of the metric (see Equation 1).

$$PA = N(1 + \sqrt{g1(S)^2 + g2(F, R)^2})$$

Equation 1. Psychoacoustic Annoyance Model [13]

This correlation is supported by Atamer and Altinsoy [14], whose research emphasized that loudness must be controlled to isolate the effects of secondary psychoacoustic parameters, such as sharpness, on annoyance ratings [14]. Within the context of mechanical switches, these findings suggest that increased loudness is a likely detractor from QoE in productivity environments.

Figure 2. Loudness vs. Annoyance [14]

Acoustic measurements of standard switch types reflect significant variants that support the development of the hypothesis. **Clicky (Blue)** switches have the highest average noise levels (approx. 64.6dB), followed by **Tactile (Brown)** switches (59.3dB), and **Linear (Silent Red)** switches (52.5dB) [15]. Given the relationship between loudness and annoyance seen in Zwicker and Fastl’s model [13], it is hypothesized that Clicky switches will yield the lowest satisfaction

ratings in a productivity context due to their loudness levels.

Figure 3. 10 Keyboard Switch Noise Level Comparison [SSSAK, 2020]

Sharpness and Acoustic Comfort. “Sharpness is a sensation value caused by high-frequency components of a given noise” [16] and is considered a critical factor in the user experience of mechanical switches. Prior research by Kosaka, Serizawa, and Watanabe [4] suggests that sharpness is a significant determinant of keyboard switch sound quality.

Words	Coefficient of Concordance w	Significance
Initially Smooth	0.43	○
Smooth	0.38	○
Deep	0.61	○
Clicking	0.60	○
Stiff	0.44	○
Arriving Shock	0.33	○
Viscous	0.21	
Quick	0.17	
Clear	0.59	○
Prefer	0.15	
High Sound	0.64	○
Loud	0.73	○
Stiff Sound	0.35	○
Sharp Sound	0.51	○

Words	χ^2	Significance
Click Sound	122.6	○

Figure 3. Significance of Sharpness on Switch Function [4]

The impact of sharpness on consumer satisfaction has been researched in other domains. In the evaluation of electric vehicle (EV) acoustics, sharpness was identified as an influential parameter in determining user preference [17]. Based on such precedents, it may be hypothesized that switch mechanisms with prominent high-frequency content might provide satisfying auditory feedback to the operator. However, within the Psychoacoustic Annoyance framework, excessive sharpness is a known contributor to discomfort, necessitating rigorous evaluation of this parameter’s behavior in a productivity context.

3. Method

Following established psychoacoustic protocol, a listening-based user experience study was conducted to integrate subjective jury evaluations with objective psychoacoustic metrics [14, 11, 17].

3.1 Subjects

17 mechanical keyboard users were recruited for the study. Comprising individuals in their early twenties to early thirties, the cohort represented a demographic who frequently use keyboards for gaming and productivity. Participants identified with diverse ethnic backgrounds, including South East Asian, European, and British. Experience levels with mechanical hardware ranged from enthusiasts to novice users.

3.2 Stimuli

While Cherry MX switches are often cited as the industry benchmark for the fundamental switch profiles [6, this study utilized **Gateron Red (Linear)**, **Gateron Brown (Tactile)**, and **Gateron Blue (Clicky)** switches. Gateron switches were selected due to their high degree of functional and structural equivalence to Cherry MX models (see Figure 4 for comparative analysis).

Cherry switches	Actuation force	Pre-travel	Travel distance	Behavior	Sound level	Suitable for
 Red switch	45 ±15gf	2 ±0.6mm	4 ±0.6mm	Linear	Quiet	Gaming/office
 Blue switch	60 ±15gf	2.2 ±0.6mm	4 ±0.6mm	Clicky	Clicky	Typist
 Brown switch	55 ±15gf	2 ±0.6mm	4 ±0.6mm	Tactile	Gentle	Midway gaming/office
Gateron switches	Actuation force	Pre-travel	Travel distance	Behavior	Sound level	Suitable for
 Red switch	45 ±15gf	2 ±0.6mm	4 ±0.6mm	Linear	Quiet	Office/gaming
 Blue switch	60 ±15gf	2.3 ±0.6mm	4 ±0.6mm	Clicky	Clicky	Typist
 Brown switch	55 ±15gf	2 ±0.6mm	4 ±0.6mm	Tactile	Gentle	Midway gaming/office

Figure 4. Comparative Analysis of Cherry MX and Gateron Fundamental Switches (18)

To isolate the switch mechanism as the primary independent variable, all stimuli were housed in **Epomaker Skyloong GK61** hardware (see Figure 5). This control measure was essential to

ensure that differences in acoustic profiles were a direct result of the switch mechanics.

Figure 5. Epomaker Skyloong GK61 [19]

3.3. Experimental Setup

3.3.1. Experimental Environment

Testing was conducted in a dedicated study area within the University of Huddersfield’s library (Room 3/09). This location was selected for its ecological validity, as it represents a typical productivity environment where mechanical keyboard use is permitted. The workspace was situated in a secluded area, shielded from high-traffic zones by shelving units; this serves to minimize visual distractions. By experimenting in a real-world productive setting rather than an anechoic chamber, the study captured the operator’s experience within a contextually appropriate acoustic framework.

3.3.2. Workstation Configuration and Stimulus Presentation

Figure 6. Experimental Setup by Cindy Loke

The experimental workstation was configured to simulate a standard dual-monitor productivity environment (see Figure 6). Participants were seated facing a primary laptop display and a secondary monitor positioned directly behind it. The secondary monitor served as the stimulus reference, displaying text passages to be transcribed, while the laptop functioned as the input

interface.

To ensure consistency, transcription tasks were divided into two categories:

1. Familiarization Phase: A long-form practice passage (see Appendix A.1) allowed participants to acclimate to the specific tactile and auditory profile of each switch mechanism.
2. Evaluation Phase: A shorter, standardized test passage (see Appendix A.2) was utilized for the actual data collection. The brevity of the test passage was a deliberate control measure to mitigate participant fatigue, ensuring that subjective ratings remained consistent across all three stimuli.

Passages were sourced via a randomized text generator.

3.3.3. Signal Chain and Data Acquisition

The laptop interface managed three coexisting software environments: a word processor for transcription, a digital survey (Google Forms) for Quality of Experience (QoE) evaluation, and a Digital Audio Workstation (DAW) for acoustic capture.

Acoustic data was captured using an omnidirectional microphone (DPA 4006) routed through an Audient iD4 audio interface into Logic Pro X. Recordings were labeled according to a standardized naming convention (e.g., “*Experiment_ID - Participant_Name - Stimulus_Code*”). Each mechanical keyboard was interfaced via a wired USB connection. To evaluate the hypothesis that elevated loudness correlates with a reduction in QoE, empirical sound pressure level (SPL) measurements were recorded using a Casella CEL-620 Sound Level Meter. The meter was positioned toward the operator’s ear canal to capture sound pressure level from the listener’s perspective (see Figure 6). Measurements were recorded using the A-weighting filter (LpA) to ensure that data reflected the frequency-dependent sensitivity of the human ear [20]. This adheres to the study’s focus on human-centered user experience. Real-time data was monitored via the meter’s interface and tabulated for correlation analysis with the subjective survey results.

The DPA 4006 omnidirectional microphone was selected for its ability to mimic the way human ears perceive acoustic energy in a room [21]. In accordance with the study’s focus on the operator’s perspective, the microphone was fitted with a diffuse-field grid (DD0251). This grid is specifically designed for use in environments with multiple reflective surfaces—such as the study area used in this study—to maintain a linear frequency response within a diffuse sound field [22]. To compensate for the high-frequency boost inherent in the microphone’s on-axis response (see Figure 7), the capsule was oriented vertically (90° relative to the sound source) as

illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 7. DPA 4006 Frequency Response with Diffuse Field Grid [23]

3.3.4. Temporal Logging and Performance Metrics

To assess the impact of switch mechanics on user performance—a potential indicator of Quality of Experience (QoE)—a digital timer was utilized to record the completion time for each transcription task. These data points allowed for the calculation of Words Per Minute (WPM) across all three stimuli, providing an objective measure of how varying tactile and auditory feedback can influence the operator's typing efficiency and response rate.

A tablet was employed as a data logger for the following parameters:

1. SPL Data: Real-time logging of LpA values obtained from the Casella CEL-620.
2. Qualitative Observations: Contextual notes regarding the participant's behavior or verbal reactions during typing tasks.
3. Structured Interview Data: Transcription of participant responses during the post-test interview phase.

This multi-device logging protocol ensured that both quantitative performance metrics (WPM and SPL) and qualitative user feedback were synchronized and preserved for correlation analysis.

3.4. Subjective Data Collection

3.4.1. Quality of Experience (QoE) Framework

To evaluate the multidimensional nature of user experience, this study inherited a QoE framework. Quality of Experience is a measure of satisfaction a user experiences when interacting with a product [24]. Subjective data was collected via a digital survey (Google Forms) and structured interviews, allowing organization of participant ratings for statistical analysis. The survey targeted six dimensions: Overall Listening Experience (OLE), perceived accuracy, haptic feedback, perceived response rate, and perceived psychoacoustic annoyance.

Overall Listening Experience (OLE)

The OLE metric provides a holistic evaluation of auditory stimuli, accounting for all factors that influence a listener's perception [25]. Evaluating OLE along with QoE could stipulate the importance of the listening experience on a user's overall experience.

Performance Metrics: Accuracy and Response Rate

Defined as “the percentage of correct keystrokes relative to the total number of inputs” [26], Accuracy is a direct indication of operator performance.

This is evident in Madison et al.'s [27] investigation, where physical variations in keyboard architecture—such as key gap—significantly impact operator response and error rates. By applying external architecture to the internal switch mechanism, this study investigates how the feedback of different switches modulates operator accuracy and overall satisfaction.

Response Rate is a measure of perceived and objective latency between the operator and a keyboard.

Prior research indicates that changes in keyboard stimuli can affect user response rates and processing speed [28]. To obtain an understanding of QoE, participants' perceived response rates were tabulated via the subjective survey, while objective typing speed (WPM) was calculated to cross-verify the performance of each switch mechanism.

Haptic Feedback is defined as “the use of tactile sensations to communicate information to an operator” [10].

Previous research on hardware ergonomics provides evidence of the complex relationship between haptic feedback and user experience. While Gerard et al. [29] observed that key stiffness may accelerate operator fatigue, Hamam and El Saddik [30] found that it improved overall QoE. On the understanding that hardware ergonomics directly influence operator performance, haptic feedback was included as a core measure in the subjective evaluation.

3.4.2. Scaling and Bias Mitigation (ITU-T P.800 ACR)

Subjective ratings for the dimension mentioned above were collected using ITU-Tp.800 Absolute Category Rating (ACR) framework. Participants were tasked to rate measures on a five-point verbal scale (see Figure 8), evaluating one stimulus at a time without comparison (see Appendix A.3). This non-comparative approach was implemented to eliminate anchoring bias, ensuring that participant evaluations of switch mechanisms were not influenced by the preceding stimulus.

Figure 8. ITU-T P.800 ACR Framework Scale [31]

3.4.3. Perceived Psychoacoustic Annoyance (PA)

Psychoacoustic Annoyance (PA) is a multidimensional metric comprising various hearing sensations that describe an annoying user encounter. By evaluating perceived PA, the study aims to quantify the effects of different switch mechanisms on global QoE.

The subjective assessment of PA followed the ICBEN (International Commission on the Biological Effects of Noise) standard. As per ICBEN protocol, two questions were utilized: a five-point verbal scale and an eleven-point numerical rating (see Figure 9 and Appendix A.3). Verbal ratings allowed identification of qualitative trends in annoyance, while the eleven-point

numerical scale provided opportunities for cross-comparison between subject responses and objective psychoacoustic metrics [32].

Card Q.V	Extremely
	Very
	Moderately
	Slightly
	Not at all

Card Q.N	
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10	
Not at all	Extremely

Figure 9. ICBEN Standard Answer Cards [Fields et al., 2001]

3.4.3. Structured Interview

Although verbal ratings are clear and quantifiable data, they restrict the assessor's ability to fully articulate nuanced experiences. To address this, a free-response structured interview was implemented, following the methodology in Atamer and Altinsoy's study [14].

Interview questions were divided into two categories (see Figure 10):

1. Contextual: Questions addressed participants' prior experiences with the mechanical keyboard and their primary use cases (i.e., gaming vs. productivity)
2. Experimental: Participants were encouraged to elaborate on their perceptions of each switch stimulus and provide descriptive context for their numerical ratings.

Interview Questions

1. Have you used mechanical keyboards before?
 - a. If so, what mechanical keyboards do you use?
 - i. What layout
 - ii. Which switches do you prefer and why do you use these switches?
 1. Is it because of the sound, accuracy, response rate
 - b. Are you interested in mechanical keyboards?
 - i. Do you modify them as a hobby?
 1. If so, do you have a preferred modification sound
 - a. What do you use mechanical keyboards for?
 2. Experiment Keyboards
 - a. Did you have a keyboard you preferred?
 - i. Why did you prefer this keyboard?
 - b. Is there a difference between this keyboard and a keyboard which sound you preferred?
 - a. If there is, what made you dislike the keyboard of which sound you liked?
 - c. Why do you prefer the sound of the keyboard you liked?
 - d. What would you change about your overall experience with the mechanical keyboards?
 3. What do you modify for and why

Thank you for coming,
Do collect a chocolate as a treat

Figure 10. Structured Interview Session by Cindy Loke

3.4. Experimental Protocol

The study followed a within-subject (repeated measures) design, where participants were exposed to all three switch stimuli. Due to the small subject pool recruited, the study could not inherit between-subject design, which requires a large group of subjects for substantial results [33].

The protocol was divided into three phases:

1. **Acclimatization Phase:** Participants familiarize themselves with the mechanical keyboard apparatus and workstation.
2. **Evaluation Phase:** Participants performed transcription tasks with each mechanical switch stimulus to generate objective and subjective data.
3. **Qualitative Phase:** A structured interview to capture nuanced user feedback.

3.4.1. Acclimatization and Preparation

To mitigate extraneous bias, the presentation of each switch type was randomized for each participant [33]. Before the participant's arrival, the experimenter initialized the data-logging tablet.

Upon entering the experimental environment, participants were instructed to adjust their seating for optimal comfort relative to the multi-screen workstation (see Figure 6). During this stage, the monitor displayed the long-form practice passage (see Appendix A.1), allowing the participant to acclimate to the mechanical switches. Simultaneously, the experimenter ensured the DPA 4006 microphone and Casella CEL-620 SPL meter were precisely aligned with the operator's ear canal to ensure a representative user perspective.

3.4.2. Evaluation Phase

Following acclimatization, the experimenter removes all mechanical keyboards from the workstation and provides a formal briefing on the evaluation procedure. This is to ensure that participants possess a clear understanding of the task requirements.

The evaluation followed a repeated measures structure:

1. **Stimulus Presentation:** The first randomized stimulus was connected, and the secondary monitor was updated to display the standardized test passage.
2. **Synchronized Data Capture:** Participants were instructed to transcribe the text onto the laptop interface, without correcting mistakes, while the experimenter initialized the DAW (Logic Pro X) and Casella CEL-620 for real-time monitoring.
3. **Subjective Assessment:** Upon completion of their task, the recording was halted. The participant then completed the digital QoE survey for that specific switch mechanism.
4. **Data Logging:** During the survey, the experimenter tabulated all recorded measurements into the data logger on the tablet.

This four-step procedure was repeated for each of the stimuli.

3.4.3. Qualitative Phase (Structured Interview)

A structured free-response interview commences upon completion of the final evaluation trial (see Figure 10).

4. Data Analysis

4.1. Objective Data Analysis and Metric Calculation

To identify the specific acoustic and performance attributes that influence mechanical keyboard Quality of Experience (QoE), a suite of objective metrics was extracted from experimental trials. These data points provided a quantitative baseline to be correlated against the subjective participant ratings.

4.1.1. Psychoacoustic Modeling

Acoustic recordings captured in Logic Pro X were exported as WAV files and processed using MATLAB's psychoacoustic toolbox. T

1. Loudness(N): Measured in Sones, correlating with the hypothesis that loudness will detract from QoE.
2. Sharpness(S): Measured in Acum, corresponding to the second hypothesis of the study: switch mechanisms with high-frequency transients might provide satisfying auditory feedback to the operator
3. Fluctuation (F): Measured in Vacil. quantifying the low-frequency modulations that contribute to the Psychoacoustic Annoyance of a product experience (see Equation 1).
4. Roughness (R): Measured in Asper. It has a relationship with Psychoacoustic Annoyance (see Equation 1).
5. Psychoacoustic Annoyance (PA): A metric that weights Loudness, Sharpness, Fluctuation, and Roughness to estimate the unpleasantness of a sound source (see Equation 1).

(see Appendix A.4 for full results)

4.1.2. Performance Metrics (WPM and Accuracy)

Operator performance was determined through direct calculation recorded during the Evaluation Phase.

Words Per Minute (WPM)

Calculated using simple math:

$$WPM = Total\ Words / Time\ in\ Minutes$$

Equation 2. Words Per Minute Equation by Cindy Loke

Typing Accuracy

As mentioned, accuracy is the percentage of correct keys pressed out of all keys:

$$Accuracy(\%) = ((Total\ Words - Total\ Errors) / Total\ Words) * 100$$

Equation 3. Accuracy Equation by Cindy Loke

(see Appendix A.4 for full results)

4.2. Statistical Analysis

Data collected via Google Forms and manual logging were organized into Google Sheets for computational analysis (see Appendix A.4). To facilitate quantitative processing within the RStudio environment, the switch stimuli were numerically coded as follows: 1 (Linear), 2 (Tactile, and 3 (Clicky). This encoding allowed streamlined execution of comparative algorithms

and the generation of visualization.

RStudio was selected for its robust statistical libraries, ensuring that the relationship between objective switch characteristics and subjective user ratings could be analyzed with precision

4.2.1. Visualization and Quantitative Mapping

The generation of analytical graphs followed a two-step protocol:

1. Data Integration: Importing structured datasets into the R environment.
2. Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA): Utilized the “ggplot2” library to generate boxplots, allowing the visualization of median scores, quartiles, and potential outliers across each switch condition.

```
OLE <- QoE_Responses[,c("Option","Rating")]
boxplot(Rating~Option,
        data = OLE,
        xlab = "Options",
        ylab = "Rating",
        main = "Overall Listening Experience Ratings",
        names = c("Option A","Option B", "Option C"),
        col = c("Red","Brown","Blue"),
        ylim = c(1,5))
```

Figure 12. Example Boxplot Code in RStudio by Cindy Loke

(see results in Appendix A.5 and A.6)

4.2.3. Inferential Statistics and Data Analytics

While the initial boxplots provided a visual overview, significant overlap in interquartile ranges necessitated deeper analysis. Utilizing “ggpubr” and “dplyr” libraries, a three-step statistical program was implemented:

1. Normality Testing

A Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to evaluate the distribution of each experimental condition (see Figure 13). The null hypothesis (H₀) assumes normally distributed data. Normality was rejected when $p \leq 0.05$ indicating non-parametric data. Conversely, if

$p > 0.05$ the null hypothesis was accepted, and the data were treated as parametric. (See results in Appendix A.7)

```
AOLE <- QoE_Responses[,c("Option...12","Rating...13")]
shapiro.test(AOLE$Rating...13)

BOLE <- QoE_Responses[,c("Option...15","Rating...16")]
shapiro.test(BOLE$Rating...16)

COLE <- QoE_Responses[,c("Option...18","Rating...19")]
shapiro.test(COLE$Rating...19)
```

Figure 13. Example Shapiro-Wilk Test in R by Cindy Loke

2. Significance Testing

To determine that performance data across all three stimuli were statistically significant, the following tests were applied:

- Parametric Data: A Repeated Measures ANOVA was performed (see Figure 14).
- Non-Parametric Data: A Friedman Test was utilized (see Figure 15).

```
anova_test(
  data = QoE_Responses,
  dv = WPM,
  wid = ID,
  within = Option
)
```

Figure 14. Example Repeated ANOVA Test in R by Cindy Loke

```
friedman.test(
  y = QoE_Responses$QoE,
  groups = QoE_Responses$Option,
  blocks = QoE_Responses$ID
)
```

Figure 15. Example Friedman Test in R by Cindy Loke

(See results in Appendix A.7)

3. Correlation Testing

To quantify the relationship between objective psychoacoustic metrics and subjective user ratings, correlation coefficients were calculated. Spearman's rank correlation was applied to non-parametric data, while Pearson's correlation was applied to parametric datasets (see Figure 16). (See correlation results in Appendix A.8)

```
cor(QoE_Responses$Option, QoE_Responses$Accums, method = 'spearman')
cor(QoE_Responses$Option, QoE_Responses$Roughness, method = 'pearson')
```

Figure 16. Example Correlation Testing in R by Cindy Loke

5. Results and Discussion

The experimental results are analyzed into two sections, aligned with the core of the research question:

1. Subjective Preference: Which *switch mechanism* is the most audibly satisfying?

2. Objective Influence: Which *psychoacoustic parameters* account for this perception?

5.1. The Relationship Between OLE and QoE

Statistical analysis revealed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.76$) between Overall Listening Experience (OLE) and Quality of Experience (QoE) (see Appendix A.8). This relationship suggests that the auditory profile of a mechanical switch is a primary driver of overall user satisfaction. Thus, variations in OLE can be used as a reliable predictor for the overall perceived quality of the user interface.

5.2. Subjective Evaluation of Switch Mechanisms

The data suggests that the introduction of a “click” noise results in a measurably unfavorable operator experience.

5.2.1. Correlation and Significance

A transition across stimuli—from Linear (1) to Clicky (3)—demonstrated a negative correlation with both QoE ($r = -0.1$) and OLE ($r = -0.2$) (see Appendix A.8). This indicates that as acoustic feedback becomes “clicky”, the perceived quality declines.

The Friedman test conducted on OLE datasets yielded a significance value of $p = 0.04$ (see Appendix A.7), confirming that the differences in user perception across the three switch types are statistically significant. Post-hoc analysis (see Figure 17) identified **Tactile switches** as the highest-rated stimuli, while **Clicky switches** were ranked the lowest in terms of auditory satisfaction.

Figure 17. OLE Ratings from Survey by Cindy Loke

5.2.2. Perceived Annoyance

Subjective annoyance, recorded via the ICBEN verbal scale, showed a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.3$) with the stimuli (see Appendix A.8). This further supports the finding that transitioning toward clicky switch mechanisms increases the operator’s perception of annoyance.

5.3. Objective Psychoacoustic Influence on Operator Preferences

5.3.1. The Role of Loudness: Sones and LAEq

The primary hypothesis of this research states that elevated loudness is the fundamental driver of user annoyance. Statistical analysis of the objective data confirmed that both Loudness (N in Sones) and Continuous Sound Level (LAEq in dBA) yielded significant results with p-values of 0.007 (see Appendix A.7).

In alignment with Zwicker and Fastl's model [13], Loudness in Sones demonstrated a strong positive correlation with Psychoacoustic Annoyance (PA). Furthermore, the strong negative correlation between OLE and subjective PA ratings (Annoyance on Verbal Scale $r = -0.9$, Annoyance on Numerical Scale $r = -0.8$) suggests that higher annoyance scores directly translate to a decreased QoE (see Appendix A.8).

5.3.2. Intra-Stimuli Loudness Variance

Despite the clear link between loudness and annoyance, the experimental data revealed mild nuances in switch performance. While **Tactile (Brown) switches** exhibit the highest median loudness (see Figures 18 and 19), interquartile ranges (IQR) for all three stimuli showed significant overlap. The differences in loudness between all three switch mechanisms are not statistically significant in this sample.

This overlap reflects that Gateron switch mechanisms do not possess distinct loudness profiles to serve as the sole indicator of user experience. This is evident by the weak correlation between stimulus type (1-3) and LAEq and objective PA (Stimuli and LAEq $r = -0.2$, Stimuli and objective PA $r = -0.1$) (see Appendix A.8).

Figure 18. Loudness (LAEq) Perceived by Participants by Cindy Loke

Figure 19. Loudness (Sones) Perceived by Participants by Cindy Loke

5.3.3. The Role of Sharpness: Acum

Following the secondary hypothesis of this study, the effect of Sharpness (S) on user experience was analyzed.

Sharpness demonstrated a weak negative correlation with QoE ($r = -0.2$) and OLE ($r = -0.2$) (see Appendix A.8), suggesting that switches with higher frequency content result in lower user satisfaction ratings. This finding aligns with Zwicker and Fastl's Psychoacoustic Annoyance (PA) model [13], where Sharpness is the secondary driver of perceived annoyance.

The significance of this metric is further supported by Atamer and Altinsoy's work [14], which found that Sharpness accounts for 18% of annoyance ratings.

5.3.4. Intra-Stimuli Sharpness Variance

Figure 18. Sharpness Perceived by User by Cindy Loke

Figure 18 illustrates Clicky switches possessing Sharpness values higher than the other two stimuli, with no overlap in the Interquartile Ranges (IQR). This spectral separation may provide an explanation for why Clicky switches were deemed the least favorable by participants.

6. Conclusion

To understand the psychoacoustic parameters that contribute to auditory satisfaction, this research asked the question: “When using a mechanical keyboard for *productivity tasks*, which *switch mechanism* is perceived as most audibly satisfying, and which *psychoacoustic parameters* account for this perception?”

It was hypothesized that switch loudness would decrease user experience ratings, while sharpness would enhance perceived satisfaction. To test this, a mixed-method listening-based user experience study was conducted, integrating subjective jury evaluations from 17 mechanical keyboard users with objective psychoacoustic metrics. Results demonstrated that Tactile (Brown) switches were the most positively rated, while Clicky (Blue) switches were the least favorable.

The data contradicted the initial hypotheses:

The Loudness Paradox: Although overall loudness exhibited a strong negative correlation with Quality of Experience (QoE), the Gateron switch conditions tested did not possess significant differences in loudness. This suggests that while loudness intensity is a driver of annoyance, it was not the psychoacoustic reason behind the user ratings of these switch types. **The Impact of Sharpness:** Unexpectedly, Sharpness (S) was the most significant differentiator of mechanical switch user experience. Contrary to the hypothesis that sharpness would provide satisfying results, it demonstrated a negative correlation with QoE. The Clicky switch mechanism exhibited significantly higher sharpness values against other stimuli, offering potential explanation for its unfavorable ratings.

6.2. Implications and Future Work

The findings suggest that the acoustic comfort of mechanical switches can be improved by modulating high-frequency spectral weighting and suppressing sharpness-related characteristics. However, due to the modest correlation strengths ($r = -0.2$) and conflicting findings from prior research, these results should be viewed as a foundation for further investigation.

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Appendix

Objective Psychoacoustic Boxplots

Sharpness Perceived by Listener

Roughness Perceived by Listener

Psychoacoustic Annoyance Perceived by Listener

Words Per Minute

Dynamic Range Perceived by Listener

Fluctuation perceived by Listener

Subjective Participant Perceptions Boxplots

Quality of Experience Ratings

Overall Listening Experience Ratings

Psychoacoustic Annoyance Rated on Verbal Scale

Psychoacoustic Annoyance Rated on Numerical Scale

Haptic Feedback Rating

Response Rated by Participants

Accuracy Rated by Participants

